
Some remarks about the relationships between the common skeleton concept within the Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez QSAR method and the weak molecule-site interactions

Juan S. Gómez-Jeria^{1,3}, Andrés Robles-Navarro¹, Gaston Assongba Kpotin², Nicolás Garrido-Sáez¹, Nelson Gatica-Díaz¹

¹Quantum Pharmacology Unit, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences, University of Chile. Las Palmeras 3425, Santiago 7800003, Chile

²Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences and Technologies, University of Abomey-Calavi, Abomey-Calavi, Republic of Benin

³Glowing Neurons Group, CP 8270745 Santiago, Chile

Corresponding author: facien03@uchile.cl

Abstract The Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez (KPG) method relates the variation of the numerical values of a biological activity, measured *in vivo* or *in vitro*, with the variation of the numerical values of a set of local atomic reactivity and orientational parameters of the substituents indices belonging to a certain skeleton, defined as a set of atoms common to all the set of molecules under study. The KPG method was developed only for weak molecule-site interactions. The local atomic reactivity indices appearing in the KPG equations allow suggesting the possible nature of the (weak) atom-site interactions. It has been found that an atom/group-site weak interaction table is urgently needed to standardize the physical interpretation of the results. We present here such a Table built from the Discovery Studio Visualizer software. We expect that this table of atom/group-atom/group interactions will also serve as a beacon of light across the path to find the possible relationships between KPG and docking studies.

Keywords Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez method, QSAR, chemical reactivity, common skeleton, weak molecular interactions, drug-site interaction, atom-atom interaction, quantum pharmacology

Introduction

Molecular interactions (intermolecular and intramolecular) are still studied experimentally and theoretically in different combinations of phases: solid-solid, solid-liquid, liquid-gas, etc [1-9]. Within this research area, the endogenous molecule-site (enzymes, neurotransmitters, etc.), drug-receptor or drug-site interactions are of paramount importance in many biological and pharmacological processes. The research area searching for relationships between the electronic structure and biological activity produces yearly a plethora of linear and nonlinear equations relating both topics. In the case of weak intermolecular interactions we expect that some structure-activity relationships allow us to get an insight on the possible nature of these interactions.

The Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez method (KPG hereafter) is a member of the class of model-based methods [10]. As a paper presenting its scientific and philosophical foundations was recently published, here we shall present only a very general description [11]. The method is based in solving a system of N linear equations relating a certain

biological activity (originally the KPG method was developed only for experimentally measured drug-receptor affinities) with a set of local atomic reactivity indices (LARIs) belonging to a molecular structure common to a group of N molecules. If we consider that each atom of this common skeleton is described by twenty local atomic reactivity indices and that the smallest common skeleton we have employed has about ten atoms, in this simplest case approximately 200 constants must be found for the system of linear equations ($N=200$). To this large set of data sometimes we must add the values of the orientational effect of the substituent. As no paper publishes the experimental data for such a large number of molecules, we cannot solve the system of linear equations. This is the only reason why the traditional techniques of Linear Multiple Regression Analysis (LMRA) are employed to find a solution. In this last case the results appear in the form of a linear equation satisfying all required statistical tests. This equation shows a relationship between the *variation* of the value of a biological activity and the *variation* of the numerical values of a set of local atomic reactivity indices. This involves two important facts. The first one is that the equation contains no LARIs having a constant value. The second fact is that the equation does not contain those LARIs the variation of whose numerical values is not statistically significant. Then, this equation displays at most the importance of *some* atoms and *some* substituents. It is important to stress that the KPG model was developed only for weak interactions (i.e., molecular interactions with no formation of covalent bonds) [12-15].

On the other hand, we have carried out some docking studies for a diversity of molecules and receptors [16-23]. Given that docking procedures are less exact than the KPG results, when we have found what at first glance seem to be discrepancies between the results of both methods, we have suggested that it is more likely that the results of the docking procedure are probably not accurate. It should be emphasized that the KPG method works with atom-atom interactions while docking techniques are not restricted to these types of interactions. However, some results of the KPG method suggest that there is a possibility that interactions of different types of a single atom with two different sites are represented through the appearance in the QSAR equation of more than one reactivity index associated with the same atom. This fact deserves more research.

To achieve this goal it seems necessary to create a Table of the different atom/group-site weak interactions. This table will also serve to standardize the interpretation of future KPG-QSAR results.

The common skeleton

The common skeleton is defined as a set of atoms, forming a connected or non-connected structure. These atoms are common to all the molecules analyzed.

Figure 1: Common skeleton of angelicin derivatives [29]

Let Θ the set of n molecules θ_i considered for a KPG study. Then:

$$\Theta = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n\}$$

Let Ξ the set of p atoms ε_i forming the common skeleton:

$$\Xi = \{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_p\}$$

Let Ω the set of all elements, τ_i , of the Periodic Table:

$$\Omega = \{\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_i\}$$

In the first applications of the KPG method atom ε_i was taken as being of the same nature in all molecules: for a given atom ε_i , $\varepsilon_i = \tau_j \quad \forall i$ (for example, the fifth atom of the common skeleton was a carbon atom in all the set of molecules under study) [24-28]. Figure 1 shows an example of this kind of common skeleton [29].

Over time the definition of common skeleton underwent two important changes. The first one was to accept that a particular atom of the common skeleton does not need to have the same nature in all the molecules. Figures 2 and 3 show some examples.

Figure 2: Common skeleton of *N*-3-benzimidazolephenylbisamide derivatives [30].

Figure 2 shows an example of common skeleton in which atom 'X' is not the same in all cases (X= S or O) [30].

Figure 3: Common skeleton of phenylaminopyridine derivatives [31].

Figure 3 shows another case in which atoms 'X', 'Y' and 'Z' are different (X, Y and Z are C or N) [31]. The second change was mainly related to substituents bonded to atoms belonging to aromatic zones of the molecules. In some QSAR studies it was not possible to obtain statistically significant results with the abovementioned definitions of the common skeleton. Good results appeared only when the local atomic reactivity indices from the atom of the substituent directly bonded to the aromatic zone were included (note that if a substituent at a certain position has two or more atoms in *all* the molecules, the common skeleton may be enlarged with these atoms). A recent possibility, that has not been tested yet, considers the case in which a common skeleton has N atoms for all but one molecules, this last one having (N-1) atoms. In this case, *only* the local atomic reactivity indices having numerical values equal or greater than 0.0 should be included for the case of the missing atom.

An additional problem is represented in the following figures. Figure 4 shows an aromatic ring of a molecule interacting simultaneously with two amino acids of the binding site through π -alkyl and π -sigma interactions (see below). It is not clear the number of atoms participating in the interaction through their π electrons.

Figure 4: Example of a simultaneous interaction of a molecule with two sites

Figure 5 shows an aromatic ring of a molecule interacting simultaneously with three sites through one π -donor, one π -cation, π -donor and two π - π T-shaped interactions (see below).

Figure 5: Example of a simultaneous interaction with four sites

The conceptual approach as a tool to use before any quantum chemical calculation

It is possible to employ the common skeleton to generate *previous* and detailed information about *possible* drug-site interactions before carrying out the electronic structure calculations or any QSAR study. For this task we need a pen, a paper, the structure of the proposed common skeleton and a list of non-bond interactions. With these elements we may create and analyze our set of molecules searching for similitudes and differences.

A Weak Molecular Interactions List

To build a preliminary list of non-bond molecular interactions, we have used the list of Discovery Studio Visualizer, v. 17.2.0.16340 from Dassault Systèmes Biovia Corporation [32] for the corresponding definitions and requirements. The definitions and requirements were copied directly from the Help section of the software. For almost all interactions we provided examples taken from our previous docking [16-23] or metallic surface-molecule interactions studies [33-37]. This Table was cited in a previous work as being an interesting starting point for future developments [11]. There are previous lists of molecular interactions [38] but we selected this one because it seems that if more complete and well ordered.

A. Hydrogen bonds

Within this category the following types are included: classical hydrogen bond, non-classical carbon hydrogen bonds (weaker hydrogen bonds), non-classical π -donor hydrogen bonds and salt bridges [32].

a1. Conventional hydrogen bonds [38-46]

Conventional hydrogen bond interactions can exist between a hydrogen bond donor atom (D) and an acceptor atom (A). Atoms N, O, P and S are considered to be classical hydrogen bond donor atoms, and hydrogen atoms are considered as hydrogen bond donors if connected to such atoms. Atoms of element types N, O, P and S are also hydrogen bond acceptor atoms if at least one electron lone pair is present.[32] Atoms of elements F, Cl, Br and I are also considered hydrogen bond acceptor atoms. If both atoms are N or O, the distance between the heavy donor and acceptor atoms is about 3.4 Å. Otherwise the distance is 3.8 Å (weak H-bond) [47]. Figures 6 and 7 show examples of conventional H-bonds.

Figure 6: Conventional hydrogen bond between molecules and amino acids (red = O, blue = N, white = H)

Figure 7. Conventional hydrogen bond between molecule and amino acid (left) and between amino acids (right) (red = O, blue = N, white = H)

a2. Salt bridge [48-58]

Salt bridge interactions are relatively strong non-bonded interactions between pairs of oppositely charged groups where hydrogen bonding also occurs. Interactions are classified as salt bridges for pairs of atoms where one atom is positively charged, one is negatively charged, and there is a hydrogen bond between them[32]. Figures 8 and 9 show some examples of this kind of interaction.

Figure 8: Examples of salt bridge interaction

Figure 9: Examples of salt bridge interaction

a3. Non-classical carbon hydrogen bonds (weaker hydrogen bonds) [59-65]

Carbon hydrogen bond interactions are considered weaker hydrogen bonds where the donor is a polarized carbon atom. A carbon atom is considered to be a donor if it is *either in an acetylene group or if it is adjacent to an oxygen or nitrogen atom* [32]. Figures 10 and 11 show some examples.

Figure 10: Examples of carbon hydrogen bond interaction.

Figure 11: Examples of carbon hydrogen bond interaction

a4. Non-classical π -donor hydrogen bond

π -donor hydrogen bond interactions are hydrogen bonds that occur between hydrogen bond donor atoms and a π ring that functions as a hydrogen bond acceptor [32]. Figures 12 and 13 show two examples of this interaction. The question of the participation of the entire π ring or part of it in this kind of interaction is not yet solved.

Figure 12: Example of π -donor hydrogen bond interaction

Figure 13: Example of π -donor hydrogen bond interaction

B. Electrostatic interactions

Within this category we include attractive charges interactions, salt bridges without hydrogen bond, π -cation and π -anion interactions [32].

b1. Attractive charge-charge interaction [66-69]

Attractive charge interactions exist between atoms bearing opposite whole or fractional formal charges that are within the charge-charge maximal distance of 5.6 Å (by default in the software) [32]. Figure 14 shows two examples of such kind of interaction.

Figure 14: Examples of attractive charge-charge interactions

b2. Salt bridge (see a2)

Salt bridge interactions are also recorded in the electrostatic category as well as in the hydrogen bonds category because they can be considered members of both [32].

b3. π -cation interactions[70-78]

π -cation interactions can exist between a positively charged atom and the electrons of a delocalized pi system [32]. Cations are considered to be atoms that have a net charge of at least +0.5. This permits the inclusion of delocalized

cationic species such as lysine and arginine side chains [32]. Figure 15 shows two examples of this kind of interactions. The question of the participation of the entire π ring or part of it in this kind of interaction is not yet solved.

Figure 15: Examples of π -cation interactions

b4. π -anion interactions[79-85]

π -anion interactions are calculated in the same manner as π -cation interactions, but only atoms with net charges of -0.5 or less are considered[32]. Figure 16 shows two examples. The question of the participation of the entire π ring or part of it in this kind of interaction is not yet solved.

Figure 16: Examples of π -anion interactions

C. Hydrophobic interactions

They include π - π stacked, π - π T-shaped, amide- π stacked, alkyl, π - σ and π -alkyl interactions.

c1. π - π stacked interactions[86, 87]

π rings are defined as planar ring systems composed of sp^2 hybridized atoms. They include (but are not confined to) aromatic rings [32]. The conditions to define this interaction are those of McGaughey et al. [88]. Figure 17 shows two examples. The question of the participation of the entire π ring or part of it in this kind of interaction is not yet solved.

Figure 17: Examples of π - π stacked interactions

c2. π - π T-shaped interactions[89, 90]

π - π T-shaped interactions happen if the following conditions are met [32]: (1). The distance between the centroid of each pair of π rings is determined to find those which fall within the π - π centroid (max. distance) cutoff distance (6

Å by default), and (2). An atom from each ring should be within the π - π closest atom (max. distance) cutoff (4.5 Å by default) [32]. Figure 18 shows a couple of examples. The question of the participation of the entire π ring or part of it in this kind of interaction is not yet solved.

Figure 18: Examples of π - π T-shaped interactions

c3. Amide- π stacked interactions

Amide- π stacked interactions occur between an amide group and a π ring [32]. Regarding the π systems the following criteria must be met: (1). The distance between the centroid of the amide group and the π rings falls within the π - π centroid (max. distance) (6 Å by default) [32] and (2). An atom from each group should be within the π - π closest atom (max. distance) (4.5 Å by default) [32]. Figure 19 shows an example. The question of the participation of the entire π ring or part of it in this kind of interaction is not yet solved.

Figure 19: Example of amide- π stacked interactions

c4. Alkyl interactions [91-96]

Alkyl groups are defined as the following non-polarized, non- π systems [32]: Mainly aliphatic amino acid side-chains. These include alanine, valine, leucine, isoleucine, methionine, selenomethionine, cysteine, proline, atoms CB, CG, and CD of lysine and atoms CB and CG of arginine [32].

Figure 20: Examples of alkyl interactions

Hydrophobic groups on ligands are contiguous sets of atoms that are not adjacent to concentrations of charge (charged atoms or electronegative atoms). A group of atoms is considered hydrophobic if their surface area is equal

or greater than the area of a methyl group multiplied by the surface area scale factor (default 0.65), which corresponds to the surface area of a chlorine atom [32]. Figure 20 shows two examples. The σ - σ stacking interaction of the cyclohexane dimer is another good example [97]. In the case of the drug-receptor interactions the σ - σ interaction should occur between occupied and empty MOs. We guess that evolution excluded interactions between occupied orbitals (four electron) or between empty orbitals (zero-electron) which are generally repulsive [98].

c5. π - σ interactions [97, 99-101]

π - σ interactions (sometimes referred to as CH- π interactions) are weak interactions between a hydrogen and a π ring system [32]. Besides the requirements of distance and relative position, the hydrogen acting as the donor can be implicit or explicit hydrogen and they must be connected to a non-aromatic carbon atom [32]. Figure 21 shows two examples. The question of the participation of the entire π ring or part of it in this kind of interaction is not yet solved.

Figure 21: π - σ interactions

c6. π -alkyl interactions

π -alkyl interactions exist where the centroids of a π ring and an alkyl group are within the alkyl centroid (max. distance) cutoff (5.5 Å by default) and they have at least one pair of atoms within the same π - π closest atom (max. dist.) cutoff as used for π - π interactions[32]. Figure 22 shows two examples. One of them has multiple π -alkyl interactions. The question of the participation of the entire π ring or part of it in this kind of interaction is not yet solved.

Figure 22: π -alkyl interactions

D. Halogen interactions [102-106]

d1. Halogen (Fluorine) interactions

Halogen (Fluorine) interactions are carbon-bound halogen interactions (C-X...B-Y) that have similar structural significance to weak hydrogen bonds [32]. Fluorine interactions (C-F...B-Y) are identified and monitored with all hydrogen donors and the specific case where B is carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen. In all cases, a maximum distance

criterion (Fluorine non-bond (max. dist.) is 3.7 Å by default) is used. When the interaction is with a hydrogen donor, the hydrogen bond angle criteria are used and the interaction is identified as both a fluorine and a hydrogen bond interaction [32]. Fluorine interactions with carbon and oxygen are limited to C=O moieties. Nitrogen interactions are limited to nucleophile nitrogen. These interactions are also limited by the same maximum distance criterion (3.7 Å by default) [32]. Figure 23 shows two examples.

Figure 23: Examples of halogen (Fluorine) interactions

d2. Halogen (Cl, Br, I) interactions

Halogen (Cl, Br, I) interactions have distance criteria defined as a fraction of the sum of the atoms' van der Waals radii (controlled by Halogen (Cl, Br, I) VDW fraction (max.)). The default fraction is 1, using the full van der Waals distance as the cutoff [32]. Non-fluorine halogen interactions to carbon and oxygen are also limited to C=O moieties. Additionally, interactions with (B-Y) N-C, N-S, N-P, S-C, S-S and S-P are considered [32]. Figures 24 and 25 show some examples.

Figure 24: Examples of halogen (Cl, Br, I) interactions

Figure 25: Examples of halogen (Cl, Br, I) interactions

E. Miscellaneous interactions

e1. Metal-acceptor interactions

Metal-acceptor interactions are analogous to hydrogen bonds and can exist between metal cations and hydrogen bond acceptors. The geometric parameters are the same as for hydrogen bonds, with the metal in place of the heavy atom hydrogen donor [32]. Figures 26-29 show some examples of this kind of interaction.

Figure 26: Metal-acceptor interaction between alizarin and a silver layer

Figure 27: Metal-acceptor interactions between indigo and a silver surface [33]

Figure 28: Metal-acceptor interactions between 9,10-di(thiophen-2-yl)anthracene and a gold surface [107]

Figure 29: Example of metal-acceptor interaction

e2. π -sulfur interactions

π -sulfur interactions can adopt two distinct configurations: face on and edge on [32]. Figure 29 shows two examples. The question of the participation of the entire π ring or part of it in this kind of interaction is not yet solved.

Figure 29: Examples of π -sulfur interactions

e3. Sulfur-X interactions

Sulfur-X interactions are found between divalent sulfur and N, O, or S atoms [32]. No examples were found in our studies.

e4. π -lone pair interactions[108-111]

A lone pair can form a favorable interaction with positively polarized π rings [32]: Hydrogen bond acceptor atoms are considered provided they do not already participate in other atom- π ring interactions. The distance between the acceptor and the ring centroid is within the π -lone pair (max. dist.) cutoff (3.0 Å by default). The angle between the acceptor-centroid vector and the normal to the ring plane is less than the π -lone pair angle (45° by default). No examples were found in our studies. The question of the participation of the entire π ring or part of it in this kind of interaction is not yet solved.

F. Unfavorable interactions

Steric bumps (they occur when the atom-atom distance is less than or equal to a threshold expressed as a fraction of the sum of the atoms' van der Waals radii), repulsive charge interactions (they occur between atoms bearing the same-signed whole or fractional formal charge, with a charge-charge max. distance is 5.6 Å by default), acceptor-acceptor clashes (when two acceptor atoms are within the acceptor-acceptor cutoff distance of 3.0 Å by default), donor-donor clashes (they occur between two donor atoms within hydrogen bonding distance) and metal repulsion (is a close interaction between a metal ion and a donor) are within this class[32]. Figures 30 and 31 show some examples.

Figure 30: Examples of unfavorable interactions

Figure 31: Examples of unfavorable interactions

It is conceptually clear that these unfavorable interactions must appear together with favorable ones.

The relationship between non-bond interactions and receptor model

In a paper devoted to the 45 years of the KPG model one of us presented a partial Table of non-bonded interactions built from the Discovery Studio Visualizer [11, 32]. Here we present a more complete Table containing also the approximate distance between the partners.

Table 1: Non-bond interactions

Category	Type	Distance (Å)
Hydrogen Bonds	Conventional H-bond	3.4, 3.8
Hydrogen Bonds	Carbon H-bond	3.8
Hydrogen Bonds	π donor H-bond	4.2
Hydrogen Bonds	Salt bridge	4.1
Electrostatic	Attractive charges	5.6
Electrostatic	π -cation	5.0
Electrostatic	π -anion	5.0
Hydrophobic	π - π stacked	6.0
Hydrophobic	π - π T-shaped	6.0
Hydrophobic	Amide- π stacked	6.0
Hydrophobic	Alkyl	5.5
Hydrophobic	π - σ	4.1
Hydrophobic	π -alkyl	5.5
Halogen	Halogen (F)	3.7
Halogen	Halogen (Cl, Br, I)	3.7
Miscellaneous	π -sulfur	4.5
Miscellaneous	Sulfur-X	4.5, 6.0
Miscellaneous	π -lone pair	3.0

On the other hand, and based on the work of Ariens, one of us suggested a simple model of the space around the binding site [11, 112]. We present a modification of that model in Figure 32.

Figure 32: A simple 2D model of the 3D volume around the binding site

We must not forget that the real situation occurs in a three-dimensional space and that many binding sites are inside complex structures formed by amino acids. We expect that thermal agitation ‘pushes’ the molecule toward a point where long-range electrostatic interactions begin to guide and orientate it until the place to engage in the final interaction with the site. This suggests that, despite their difference in biological activity, the molecules able to interact with a given binding site must have a very similar molecular electrostatic potential structure at about 6-6.5 Å. Figure 32 highlights the importance of π systems in several kinds of weak molecule-site interactions. We must distinguish between two processes. The first one involved the guiding of the molecule toward the binding site. The second one is the action of those short-range interactions that start a certain process leading ultimately to the manifestation of a biological activity.

In summary, we have proposed a Table of atom-atom weak interactions to be employed for the analysis of the KPG-QSAR results and for the study of the possible connections between these results and the ones coming from the field of docking studies.

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